

Islamic Hedging

Rationale, Necessity, and Challenges

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Islamic Hedging: Rationale, Necessity, and Challenges[#]

By

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Abstract

Investors and players in the financial market are exposed to various types of risks. Some of them are manageable and the others are not. Financial derivatives are financial instruments used for trading risk. The main purpose of derivatives is to distribute risk among the market players and if this distribution is done correctly then every market player will be better off, leading to the productivity and efficiency. Financial derivatives can be used for many purposes but in reality they are mostly used for just one of three basic functions: hedging, arbitrage, and speculation. However, the objective of *true hedging* is the reduction of risk that is been assumed through trading and investment. Therefore, the purpose of a hedge is to protect the value of a current or anticipated cash market or off-balance sheet position from adverse changes in interest rate. From an Islamic point of view, there is no doubt that Islam calls for wealth protection and as such, any exposure of wealth to unnecessary risk is something that is not desirable. Having this in mind, it is worth mentioning here the legal maxims that may be related to the hedging: (a) "Harm must be eliminated" (*Ad-dararu yuzal*); & (b) "Hardship begets facility" (*Al-mashaqqatu tujlab at-taysir*). The authors argue that there is a necessity for a true hedging in Islamic finance and that without the alternatives the development of Islamic finance may be at stake. However, careful analysis and clear regulations of the Islamic derivatives is highly needed as to avoid future financial crises such the current one caused by the conventional derivatives.

Key words: Islamic derivatives, hedging, risk, *gharar*, Islamic finance, global crisis

JEL Classification: D8, G01, G1, G32,

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1. Introduction

Islamic finance industry experienced extraordinary growth over the past couple of decades. New players are entering the market in anticipation of the continuing growth and success. The core principles of Islamic finance are based on *Shari'ah* (Islamic law) with two main sources, Qur'an and Sunnah.

The debate on permissibility of financial derivatives in Islamic finance is still ongoing and many issues are yet to be settled. On the other hand, the derivative instruments in conventional financial system are well developed and structured to the utmost perfection. Although the main difference between the Islamic and conventional financial systems lies in the prohibition of the interest (*riba*) there are also some other issues that are arising when structuring Islamic derivative instruments. Some of these issues are prohibition of gambling (*maysir*), excessive uncertainty (*gharar*) and speculation. Other than the issues mentioned above, all transactions in the Islamic finance have to be permissible (*halal*), with underlying asset in existence and mutual consent of both parties entering the contract (Siddiqui, 2007; Smolarski, Schapek, & Tahir, 2006).

This study aims at identifying and verifying the need, necessity, and challenges faced by the Islamic finance with regard to the development of Islamic derivative instruments. Since the current crisis is very much affected by the conventional derivative instruments it is timely for us to address the issue and find out its implication on the development of Islamic derivative instruments. With this in mind the study makes an attempt to clarify some of the issues mentioned above which are still debated in the literature.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the financial derivatives behind the current financial crisis. Namely, it discusses the collateralised debt obligations (CDOs), and credit-default swaps (CDSs). The way how the CDSs are structured in the conventional system is elaborated together with the problems faced with this sector. Section III discusses the financial derivatives from Islamic perspective. Here the issues such as hedging, its need and necessity are highlighted. Next, in Section IV the attempt is made to differentiate between the risk and *gharar*.

The necessity of the risk for the validity of a contract and the prohibition of *gharar* are discussed. Section V is briefly elaborating and highlighting the *fiqhi* issues with regard to Islamic hedging. Finally, Section VI is left for concluding remarks and recommendations.

2. Derivatives – Overview

Due to pure management and lack of proper due diligence by banks and financial institutions, the conventional financial system has fallen into the abyss of a new great depression, accelerated by the sub-prime mortgage crisis, collateralised debt obligations (CDOs), and credit-default swaps (CDSs). The Islamic finance industry is not immune to the current financial crisis. Luckily, Islamic derivatives have not developed very much in recent years and due to this conservatism this sector has been saved (at least partially) from the disastrous effects of the current credit crunch (Williams, 2009).

On one side, Islam seeks the protection of wealth and on the other, it prohibits speculation (*maysir*) and interest (*riba*). These two (*maysir* and *riba*), fuelled by greed and self-interest, had been the main catalysts of the current global crisis. How financial derivatives played a role in the current global crisis is the topic of the following paragraphs.

2.1 Derivatives and the Current Global Crisis

As mentioned earlier, the current global turmoil had been fuelled by the sub-prime mortgage crisis, collateralised debt obligations (CDOs), and credit-default swaps (CDSs). To understand how derivatives, such as those mentioned above, are related to the global financial crisis, we will look at the most commonly used derivative instrument, known as a credit-default swap or CDS.

A CDS is one of the most popularly used credit derivatives; it allows the trading of counterparty risk from one to another without changing the ownership of an underlying instrument. Investopedia defines a CDS as “a swap designed to transfer the credit exposure of fixed-income products between parties” (Investopedia, 2007). Ilya I Gikhman (2008, p. 5)

defines it as “an over-the-counter (OTC) bilateral financial instrument used to hedge the default risk of a risky debt instrument or a basket of risky debt instruments.”

The debate is still on as to whether CDSs had been responsible for the present credit chaos. However, no one denies that they played a major role, although they may not be the primary reason for the debacle. Initially these financial instruments had been responsible for the sub-prime lending fiasco, which led to the economic crisis in the United States and eventually turned into a global crisis.

2.2 How Does a Credit-Default Swap Work?

The answer to this question is quite straightforward. For example, Customer A buys corporate bonds from Company X. Customer A believes that Company X will make money and be able to pay him back with interest. Nevertheless, there is still some risk that the company will default and the bonds will be worthless. If Customer A invests a huge amount of the money in this company, he may not be willing to take the risk of losing everything; so he may decide to buy insurance, just in case Company X goes bankrupt (refer to Figure 1).

He approaches Bank Z and asks if it is willing to sell him insurance against Company X's bond. If the Bank Z thinks it is worth the risk, it may insure it at, say, a 2% premium. Now, if the Customer A bought RM1 million worth of bonds, then he has to pay RM20,000/year to Bank Z for insurance against the bonds. However, if Company X goes bankrupt, then he can still collect his RM1 million from Bank Z (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Pure Hedging

- 1) Investor/Customer A buys the corporate bonds for RM1 million.
- 2) Company X pays back principal amount plus interest to the Investor/Customer A.
- 3) Investor/Customer A buys insurance policy from Bank Z at 2% of the principal amount, i.e. RM20,000.
- 4) In case Company X defaults, the Investor/Customer A will receive the full amount from Bank Z.

Up to this point, this swap arrangement is no different from fire insurance on someone's house (i.e. you pay a premium and if your house burns down, then you collect your money from the insurer). However, there is a difference. Unlike fire insurance, Customer A does not have to actually own the asset to insure it. What does this mean? It means that, as in the case of the example above, if Customer A thinks Company X is going down, he can buy insurance against the latter's bonds from Bank Z, even if he does not actually own the bonds. This is pure speculation, and Bank Z is no longer insuring against real assets - it is offering pieces of paper (derivatives) that could cost it many times over the bonds' value (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Pure Speculation

- 1) Since there is no requirement to own the asset, the Investor/Customer A buys an insurance policy from Bank Z, believing that Company X will go bankrupt.
- 2) In case Company X in fact goes bankrupt, Investor will receive the insured amount from Bank Z.

Now, the question may be raised: Why is it a problem? Is not Bank Z supposed to have a reserve to pay people if they start making claims? Well, here lies part of the problem. Since the CDS market is completely unregulated and Bank Z is not required to have a certain percentage of reserves before offering insurance, the payments, once they are due, may not be made.

Things get more complicated or worse because Bank Z not only sells the insurance but is also out buying insurance from other banks to mitigate its own risks. This is the real problem in the financial market. In other words, if Customer A bought insurance against Company X, he is counting on Bank Z to pay up in the event of a default (i.e. he is transferring his risk from Company X to Bank Z). However, since Bank Z also bought some insurance from Bank Y, then Bank Z is counting on Bank Y to pay up in case of default. Now, this means that if Company X defaults on its payments, Customer A will receive his insured amount only if Bank Y pays that amount to Bank Z, which would only then pay it to Customer A.

Unfortunately, the buying and selling of this insurance goes on and on until every bank (investor, hedge fund, pension fund or any other financial institution) is somehow interdependent on every other bank in the CDS market. It means that almost all players in the CDS market are caught in the CDS web; if Bank Z (or Bank Y or any other bank) defaults on its insurance, then Customer A will not get his money.

However, this is not the end of the mess since Customer A was probably selling insurance as well. Since he was counting on Bank Z's money, he will not be able to pay off his insurance either. So, this problem amplifies until a vast number of the banks in the CDS

market are completely wiped out. We also should not forget that there is no underlying asset that is worth anything because Customer A did not have to own the bonds to obtain insurance against them; they were simply pieces of paper being bought and sold. The scenario above may be best depicted by the following 2 figures (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3: Real CDS Market

Where: **B** – buys insurance
S – sells insurance

Figure 4: Real CDS Market (web)

Where: **B** – buys insurance
S – sells insurance

It is due to the problems above with the CDS market that the American government keeps pumping money into AIG and Bear Stearns. These had been big players selling and buying such insurance, and did not have the money to pay up the claims that came in. Now, the reason why the government pumps in the money is to avoid bigger financial crisis that may start a domino effect, i.e. the government worries that if AIG and Bear Stearns default, then everyone counting on them to pay up will have to default as well. This situation is best described by the famous notion “Too big to fail.”

2.3 The Problems Faced by the Derivatives Market

The derivatives market is far from perfect. Derivatives have been described as evil, acts of Satan, time bombs and weapons of mass destruction. For example, Warren Buffett describes derivatives as both "financial weapons of mass destruction" and "time bombs". In his Berkshire Hathaway letters to shareholders, he said (Buffet),

Unless derivatives contracts are collateralised or guaranteed, their ultimate value also depends on the creditworthiness of the counterparties to them. In the meantime, though, before a contract is settled, the counterparties record profits and losses – often huge in amount – in their current earnings statements without so much as a penny changing hands. The range of derivatives contracts is limited only by the imagination of man (or sometimes, so it seems madmen).

From the above discussion, the problems may be deduced and listed down as follows:

- 1) *No Regulation* – It is obvious that the CDS contracts are carried over-the-counter and there are no rules and regulations governing them. The transactions are simply done over the phone or through e-mail. Due to their huge presence in the market and their influence on the stability of not only the American financial system but also the global one, the CDS market has to be regulated and monitored. If there had been regulation in place, then someone would have known that these types of transaction were a crisis waiting to happen; they could have intervened and taken the necessary actions to stop future transactions from taking place.

- 2) *No Reserve Requirement* – So far, the players in the CDS market have not had to have any reserves with regard to the insured amounts. This implies that in the event of default, the protection seller has no money at hand to cover the losses. The problem goes on through the domino effect, causing financial chaos all over the place. Had these types of derivatives been regulated, then the governing body would have made sure that the protection seller had sufficient reserves at hand to cover the losses. If the reserve requirement ever dipped below the required amount, the regulatory body would have stepped in to rectify the process.

- 3) *No Underlying Asset* – As investors, we do not have to possess the asset in order to purchase insurance. CDSs resemble an insurance policy, as they can be used by debt owners to hedge or insure against a default on a debt. However, because there is no requirement to actually own any asset or suffer a loss, CDSs can also be used, and are used, for speculative purposes.
- 4) *No Transparency* – Since this market is unregulated, no one knows how much CDS is out there, or who is who in that market (i.e. who is the seller and who is the buyer of the protection). According to International Swaps and Derivatives Association¹, the notional amount outstanding of CDS decreased by 12% in the first six months of 2008 to USD54.6 trillion from USD62.2 trillion. This means that there are still some USD50 trillion of CDS out there, somewhere, in the market.

3. Financial Derivatives from Islamic Perspective

Investors and players in the financial market are exposed to various types of risk. In other words every investment involves a certain degree of risk and expected return. Some of them are manageable while others are not. “A derivative instrument is simply a financial instrument or asset that derives its value from the value of underlying asset” (Mohamad & Tabatabaei, 2008). Financial derivatives, according to Sami al-Suwailem (2007, p. 29), are financial instruments used for trading risk. In his view, the purpose of derivatives is to distribute risk among the market players; if this distribution is done correctly, then every market player will be better off, leading to productivity and efficiency. The key fact here is that financial risk occurs naturally in a world without derivatives, and derivatives could be used to reduce, or hedge, that risk.

Financial derivatives can be used for many purposes. In reality, however, they are mostly used for just one of three basic functions: hedging, arbitrage or speculation. Hedgers use derivatives to manage uncertainty, and speculators use derivatives to bet on it. Hedgers use derivatives to reduce financial risk, or the prospect that the price of things might “move against them” (Eales & Choudhry, 2003). On the other hand, arbitrageurs and speculators use hedging to take advantage

¹ For more details see: International Swaps and Derivatives Association at <http://www.isda.org/>.

of price differences in the market and to make a profit from simple speculation on the market moves, respectively.

Generally speaking, derivatives are excellent tools of risk management known as hedging. In essence, hedging involves recognising and measuring the financial risk of an existing position, then taking on some new position with opposite exposure characteristics such that the gains and losses of the positions cancel each other out. Simply, hedging can be seen as insurance policy against unexpected movements in the market.

3.1 Debate on Islamic Hedging

In short hedging refers to a financial technique of reducing or eliminating risks (Mohamad, 2009, p. 5). The debate on permissibility of Islamic hedging is still going on with a greater attention being given to the topic in the midst of the current global financial crisis and its connection with some financial derivatives as discussed earlier in this paper. Muslim scholars are divided over the form of Islamic derivatives and their permissibility. *Shari'ah* scholars are generally of opinion that derivative instruments are not permissible on the ground that they involve, to some extent, *riba*, *gharar* and speculation (Obaidullah, 2001). According to Salahuddin Ahmed (2006) the element of certainty is important for the validity of the contract. Since the trading in options and futures contain the elements of uncertainty and speculation they are prohibited.

On the other hand, those who believe that financial derivatives have a role to play in Islamic finance and that are in line with *Shari'ah* objectives are taking proactive role in finding solutions that may solve the issues raised by the opponents. It is worth noting here that Muslim scholars are generally agreeable that Islamic hedging, in its true sense, is permissible and necessary. However, due to the small deference between hedging and speculation (the former being lawful while the latter is not) many scholars still have some reserves towards Islamic hedging (Mohamad & Tabatabaei, 2008).

The detailed discussion on hedging is presented by Al-Suwailem (2007) whereby he compared *gharar* with the game theory. *Gharar* contract, based on his discussion, are characterized as a zero-sum game where one party is to gain, but only at the expense of the other party. The hedging, although in its pure sense (i.e. protection of the possible loss or value preservation) is desired and in line with *maqāsid al- Shari'ah*, - according to Al-Suwailem - involves *gharar* and as such constitutes a zero-sum game that is prohibited. Al-Suwailem analogy is far from being perfect as El-Gamal (2001, pp. 6-7) proved that certain zero-sum exchanges are not forbidden on the basis of *gharar* and that certain contracts are forbidden on the basis of *gharar* without having zero-sum component.

On the other hand, among those who believe that derivatives in general and hedging in particular are not only allowed but also desirable are Kamali (2007), Bacha (1999, 2003), Al-Saati (2003), Obaidullah (2001) and to some extent Mohamad & Tabatabaei (2008), just to name a few.

The reason for prohibition of *gharar*, according to Al-Saati (2003) is to avoid dispute and by using *istihsān* and based on *maslahah* as a measure there is possibility to stipulate certain conditions in order to reduce the *gharar* involved in contemporary financial transactions. This mechanism would make futures, options and swap somehow acceptable (Al-Saati, 2003, p. 15). Apart from looking from an Islamic legal point of view, Bacha (1999, p. 30) suggested taking another look into equity derivatives with social welfare in mind. He said that due to the current Muslim jurists' objection there are two implications on the preservation of value and wealth creation of Muslim businesses: i) it makes the Muslim businesses vulnerable to value loss since there is a limited number of risk management instruments; and ii) this approach will make these businesses less competitive (Bacha, 1999, p. 19).

3.2 Is Hedging Desirable in Islam?

In banking, finance, and treasury operations, the objective of *true hedging* is the reduction of risk that has been assumed through trading and investment. Therefore, the purpose of

hedging is to protect the value of a current or anticipated cash market or off-balance-sheet position from adverse changes in interest rates. There is no doubt that Islam calls for wealth protection; as such, any exposure of wealth to unnecessary risk is not desirable. In this regard, Kamali (2007, p. 315) says “Since protection of property is one of the objectives (*maqasid*) of *Shariah*, it may be argued that failure to protect one’s property in the face of risk and bankruptcy is reprehensible.” Al-Sacati goes further by saying that it is a requirement on both buyers and sellers to “take protective measures against actual and potential harm (*darar*).

In other words, exposing one’s wealth to unnecessary risks goes against the spirit of *Shari’ah* and can be considered as damage (*darar*) that has to be avoided according to the legal maxims (Al-Saati, 2002). Having said this, it is worth mentioning the following legal maxims (Mejelle, 2007, pp. 5-7):

1. “Harm must be eliminated” (*Ad-dararu yuzāl*)
2. “Hardship begets facility” (*Al-mashaqqatu tujlab at-taysīr*)

Although the risk and *darar* may not be possible to eliminate it can be reduced using risk management tools. This will be done in light with the following legal maxims mentioned in *Mejelle*: “Severe damage (*darar*) is made to disappear by a lighter damage,” “The smaller of two harms (*sharr*) is chosen,” “Damage (*darar*) is repelled as far as possible.”

Therefore, hedging plays an important role in preserving social well-being. By hedging, the wealth of people (be they investors, traders or simple individuals) is protected from financial calamities and losses. Therefore controlling and/or reducing the risk are not only considered to be *mubāh*² but rather it is considered *mandūb*³ as it aims at protecting the wealth of the people (Al-Qarri, 2008).

² *Mubāh* (in Arabic مباح) is one of the classifications of an action according to Islamic Jurisprudence (*fiqh*). It is a term that denotes an action as neither forbidden nor recommended. It means 'permitted based on individuals' whim'. This category is left undecided and without a ruling by scholar so it is left for a person to decide for themselves if they do things such as eating apples or oranges. Doing or not doing the *mubāh* does not count as a good or bad deed. See <http://www.islamic-dictionary.com>.

There are other benefits of hedging, e.g. they enable businesses to plan better, leading to less price fluctuations that will then reduce costs, thus bringing further benefits to society (Bacha, 1999, p. 12). Even arbitrage brings benefits to society through the process of price realignment. According to Bacha (1999, p. 13), arbitrage enhances the discovery process. He goes further by saying that arbitrage helps reduce the distortionary effects of government regulation/intervention. Quite contrary to hedging and arbitrage, speculation hurts more than it helps. Due to the increased volume of trading, however, transaction costs will decrease and there will be more liquidity. Nevertheless, this kind of contribution by the speculation does not render it permissible in itself.

3.3 Hedging vs. Speculation

A simple way to distinguish investors from speculators is that the former risk their own capital with the hope of making profits from volatility in market prices. By hedging, they seek to offset some potential losses. On the other hand, speculators typically use the capital of others – often borrowed or trusted money – and assume the risk that investors seek to avoid. Like investors, speculators do not want to lose *their* capital. However, in the search for increasingly more profits they expose themselves to greater risks. In fact, both investors and speculators do everything possible to minimise risk and maximise returns, trying to enter the market at the right time and the right price. Nevertheless, because they are using their own money, the investors are more precautionous.

3.4 Need and Necessity for Islamic Hedging

As we have already mentioned previously, the hedging is seen as a part and parcel of *maqāsid al-Shari'ah* as its true objective is to protect one's property (Al-Suwailem, 2007, p. 56; Kamali, 2007, p. 315). Furthermore, without risk management tools, Muslim businesses will be exposed to the unnecessary loss and there will be capital flight from non-hedged funds to the hedged ones. This will further increase the cost of capital for business, making

³ *Mandūb* (in Arabic مندوب) is a recommended action, praiseworthy; a course of conduct which earns good deed if followed, for example praying extra prayers (*nāfilah*); however a person who does not follow such a course of conduct is not open to punishment. It is also synonymous with *mustahabb*.

the overall economy less competitive and this will be a huge social cost to the economy as whole (Bacha, 2003, p. 31).

Consequently, in order for Muslims to make their businesses more competitive and less vulnerable to the risk associated with the everyday business, we need risk management tools that are in line with *Shari'ah*. As such, derivative instruments (once in line with *Shari'ah* parameters) are fulfilling the general need of the people and are in line with *maslahah*. Nevertheless, the *maslaha* alone is not sufficient to make the derivative instruments permissible (Obaidullah, 2002; Siddiqui, 2007, p. 65)

While some authors are opposing the permissibility of forwards, futures and options, others consider them as valid contracts from *Shari'ah* perspective as they serve an important role in protecting the Muslim investors from unnecessary risks (*maslahah*). By not having derivative instruments, Bacha (1999) argues, Muslim investors will be at disadvantage compared to the conventional ones. Still, before we make a final conclusion on the derivatives from Islamic perspective we have to fully understand the cost and benefits of the derivative instruments (Siddiqui, 2007, p. 66). The next step would be to clarify all the *Shari'ah* issues with regard to the structure and implementation of those instruments. Finally, once endorsed, these instruments have to be monitored and under continuous supervision by the authority as to avoid harmful speculation and extensive leveraging.

Reducing the possibility of financial loss and controlling of the risk is not new to the Islam. It is reported in Sunan al-Bayhaqi that Abbas (r.a.) when he was giving his *māl* (property) to the *mudārib*, he would stipulate the following conditions: (i) not to take property (livestock) onboard a ship; (ii) not to lodge in a valley; and (iii) not to buy any live animals; and if he were to do so he would be liable for it. Then he refer the matter to the Prophet (s.a.w.s.) and he approved it (Al-Bayhaqi, 1994, p. 111).

كان العباس بن عبد المطلب إذا دفع مالا مضاربة اشترط على صاحبه أن لا يسلك به بحرا ولا ينزل به واديا ولا يشتري به ذات كبد رطبة فإن فعل فهو ضامن فرفع شرطه إلى رسول الله صلى الله عليه و سلم فأجازه

4. Risk vs. *Gharar*

Before we proceed, it will be useful to clarify the meaning of two terms: risk and *gharar* (uncertainty). The questions that are arising are: Are these two terms equivalent? Or do they mean something different? Obviously, there is no clear distinction between the two. Although some writers translate *gharar* (غرر) as risk, the term in Arabic that describes the risk best is *khatar* (خطر) (Baalbaki & Baalbaki, 2008).

Distinguishing feature between the two lies in the ability to make probability assessment. Risk, then, refers to the events that can be associated with given probability while uncertainty refers to the events for which probability assessment is not possible. This means that risky events are easier to evaluate (Chavas, 2004).

The Oxford Dictionary of Economics defines the risk as “[t]he fact that the results of any action are not certain, but may take more than one value. Risk is usually used to describe the form of uncertainty where, while the actual outcome of an action is not known, it is expected that it will be determined as the result of a random drawing from a set of possible outcomes whose distribution is known” (Black, 2003).

Ibn Taymiyyah (728H – 1328G) defined the risk (*khatar*) as follows:

“Risk falls into two categories: commercial risk, where one would buy a commodity in order to sell it for profit, and rely on Allah for that. This risk is necessary for merchants... and although one might lose sometimes this is the nature of trade.

The other type of risk is that of gambling, which implies eating people’s wealth for nothing. This is the type that Allah and His Messenger (pbuh) have prohibited.” (Al-Suwailem, 2007, p. 61)

Looking deeply into the technical meaning of the *gharar* we will see that there is a slight difference between the risk and *gharar*. Literal meaning of *gharar* is danger, deception, illusion, conceit that is derived from Arabic verb *gharra* (غَرَّ) which means to deceive, to delude, to mislead, etc (Madina, 2001). *Gharar*, on the other hand, does not have a precise definition. In

broad terms, it refers to uncertainty, hazard, chance, risk and uncertainty (Obaidullah, 1999, 2001) as well as to deception and delusion (Al-Suwailem, 2007). From its linguistic origin the term *gharar* refers to something with a pleasant appearance and unpleasant reality (Al-Darir, 1995, p. 48; El-Gamal, 2001, p. 5).

Prophet (s.a.w.s.) prohibited *gharar* due to its speculative nature that may lead to disputes, unfair gain or “eating other people’s wealth unlawfully” (اكل مال الناس بلباطل). Although the extensive *gharar* is prohibited as it can lead to disputes there are also some *gharar* transactions that are permissible based on the *maslahah*. According to Ibn Taymiyyah, “*Gharar* describes things with unknown fate. Selling such things is *maysir* and gambling” (Al-Suwailem, 2005, p. 78). Consequently, the *gharar* can be defined as the sale of probable goods whose existence and/or characteristics are not certain and due to these reasons this trade is akin to gambling.

The risk, as understood by today’s economic professionals does not belong to this prohibition as it would render every transaction as unlawful. Therefore, it is very much important to distinguish between the two as labelling them the same will lead to hardship and difficulties in everyday economic transactions. Risk in any transaction may exist due to many reasons. It can be due to the natural causes (e.g. good weather conditions or not), time allocation outcome (e.g. whether or not you will have job or not), market outcome (e.g. rise or fall in prices of the commodities; drop or rise of exchange rate), etc. The existence of all of these risks (and others not mentioned above) is inevitable in everyday transaction. As such the existence of the risk alone does not render a contract invalid. On the other hand, however, the existence of the elements of *gharar*, as described by classical Islamic jurists, is *de facto* making a contract invalid.

To sum up, the risk is something that is beyond our control, while *gharar* (uncertainty) is within our reach and control. In other words, *gharar* is the result of our ignorance or fault. Another difference between the risk and *gharar*, as can be concluded from the above discussion, is that the latter is part of the contract (i.e. it exists at the initial contract) while the former is beyond the contract (Al-Saati, 2003).

4.1 Risks in Islamic Finance

Risk and *gharar* are very much important elements of Islamic finance. On one hand, a profit without assuming a certain risk and/or obligation is non-*halal*, according to the well-known legal maxim “*al-kharaj bi al-daman*,” and is deemed to be equal to *riba*. On the other, however, excessive risk makes a contract, and therefore the profit resulting from that contract, tantamount to the sale of *gharar* and as such is prohibited.

From the above discussion we come to a simple conclusion that risk is necessary for a valid contract and that it is its excessiveness combined with the elements of *gharar* that make a contract invalid. This implies that the issue in Islamic hedging is the issue of quantifying the degree of the riskiness. Therefore, Islamic scholars have stipulated the following three conditions for tolerable risk (Al-Suwailem, 2005, p. 82):

- i) It should be negligible;
- ii) It should be inevitable; and
- iii) It should be unintentional.

4.2 Types of Risks

By and large there are two broad types of the risks, namely primary and secondary risks. The former refer to the unavoidable risk associated with each and every business while the later can be eliminated or hedged by using different financial derivatives (Al-Saati, 2002). The primary risks usually cannot be isolated completely but they can be partially reduced. For instance, a farmer cannot eliminate price risk but he can reduce it partially by entering into a forward contract selling all or part of his future harvest.

According to Ahmed and Khan (2007), Islamic banks (as well as Islamic institutions in general) are faced with two types of risks: risks similar to those faced by conventional financial institutions and risks that are related to their compliance with *Shari'ah* (p. 144). To put it differently, Islamic financial institutions in general, apart from some traditional risks, are faced with some unique risks due to the nature of their underlying contracts (Sundararajan & Errico, November 2002). Likewise, there are numerous types of risks that

are relevant to the capital market in general and Islamic finance in particular. Most commonly discussed types are: i) market/price risk, which refers to the changes in the market prices of an asset; ii) inflation risk, which negatively affects purchasing power; iii) interest rate risk that may cause change in the price of asset due to the interest rate changes or it may increase the cost of the funds; iv) default/credit risk, a risk of default on payment by the debtor; v) liquidity risk, which refers to the asset's trade frequency; and vi) currency/foreign change risk, which refers to the potential loss due to the change in the exchange rate between the currencies (Bacha, 2003, p. 6)

4.3 Creation of Wealth vs. Zero-Sumness

Risk is inevitable in the economic activities. They are seen as “part and parcel of financial intermediation” (Akkizidis & Khandelwal, 2008, p. 28). Every action taken by an economic man will be subject to a certain degree of risk as there is no “risk-free enterprise” (Al-Saati, 2002, p. 5). However, this type of risk alone does not render a contract invalid.

Zero-sum games could be defined as “games in which the interests of both parties are in direct opposition” (Al-Suwailem, 2005, p. 78). Zero-sumness is also not a sole reason for rendering a contract valid or invalid. There are contracts that are zero-sum games in nature but they are allowed due to the general public interest (*maslahah*) that they bring and because such *maslahah* cannot be achieved without taking into consideration that zero-sum game (El-Gamal, 2001, pp. 6-7).

The *raison d'être* for prohibition of *gharar* sales, as stated by many, is the excessive risk involved (El-Gamal, 2001). This is supported by the *Qur'anic* prohibition of wine and gambling where Allah (swt) says:

يَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الْخَمْرِ وَالْمَيْسِرِ قُلْ فِيهِمَا إِثْمٌ كَبِيرٌ وَمَنَافِعُ لِلنَّاسِ وَإِثْمُهُمَا أَكْبَرُ مِن نَّفْعِهِمَا
وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ مَاذَا يُنْفِقُونَ قُلِ الْعَفْوَ كَذَلِكَ يُبَيِّنُ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ الْآيَاتِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَتَفَكَّرُونَ

“They ask thee [O Muhammad] concerning wine and gambling. Say: “In them is great sin, and some benefit for mankind; but the sin is greater than the benefits”.”
[2:219]

5. *Fiqh* Issues in Hedging

As discussed in the previous sections, hedging in its true form serves an important role in protecting the wealth and as such is part and parcel of *maqāsid al-Shari‘ah* (Objectives of *Shari‘ah*). Still, Islamic hedging is far from being clear cut, as there are several issues that are still discussed and debated. Some of these issues are briefly discussed below:

- i. *Non-existence of the good* – This is considered as one of the most important issues with regard to Islamic hedging. For the true sale to be valid the subject matter of the sale needs to be in existence at the time of the sale. The Prophet (s.a.w.s.) said: “*Sell not what is not with you.*”⁴

حكيم بن حزام - رضي الله عنه - قال : قلتُ : يا رسولَ الله : إنَّ الرجلَ ليأتيني ، فيريدُ مني البيع ،
وليس عندي ما يطلبُ ، أفأبيع منه ، ثم أبتاعه من السوق ؟ قال : « لا تبِعْ ما ليسَ عندك » (Ibn Al-
(Athīr

- ii. *Non-delivery of goods and cash settlement* – Another issue that attracted a lot of debate among Muslim scholars is that the majority of investors have no intention of making or taking delivery of the underlying asset (Bacha, 1999). As there is no transfer of property these investors are seen as speculators. In addition to that, these contracts are usually concluded through cash settlement i.e. settlement in price difference. This means that the true sale never takes place (Bakar, 2008).

- iii. *Short selling and issue of qabd (non-possession of the good prior to resale)* – Short selling is not permissible according to the *Shari‘ah* rulings. The conventional practice of short selling refers to the borrowing a security and selling it on the market with

⁴ Narrated by Al-Tirmidhi and Abu Dawud and Al-Tirmidhi stated that this hadith has the status of *hasan*.

expectation that the price will go down, which would allow the initial seller (investor) to purchase it at a lower price. The above *hadith* of the Prophet (s.a.w.s.) “*Sell not what is not with you*” applies here as well.

This implies that a seller must possess a good prior to selling it to a buyer. However, most jurists are of opinion that the ownership condition is applicable only to the specified objects and not to fungible goods that can be easily replaced and substituted (Al-Saati, 2002; Dusuki, 2008). Kamali (2007) is of opinion that this prohibition is confined to foodstuffs only. Extending this prohibition to other commodities, he says, is not supported by the text (p. 335).

- iv. *Issue of sale of one debt for another (bay^c al-kāli’ bi al-kāli’ or bay^c al-dayn)* – General consensus is that the sale of debt for debt is prohibited (El Gari, 1993; Ibn Qudamah, 1995, p. 448 & 682; Ibn Taymiyyah, 2005, pp. 522-523). The rationale for the prohibition of *bay^c al-dayn* lies in the uncertainty of its repayment (Kamali, 2007, p. 326). The following *hadith* is quoted as evidence on the subject: Musa ibn ^cUqbah reported Nafi^c and he reported from Abdullah ibn ^cUmar that the Prophet (s.a.w.s.) prohibited *bay^c al-kāli’ bi al-kāli’*.⁵

عن موسى بن عقبة عن نافع عن ابن عمر رضي الله عنهما : أن النبي صلى الله عليه و سلم نهى عن بيع الكالئ بالكالئ (Al-Naysaburi, 1990, p. 65)

- v. *Issue of speculation, gambling and gharar* – There is a very tiny line between true hedging and speculation (Mohamad & Tabatabaei, 2008), and thus between speculation, gambling and *gharar*. It is very difficult to differentiate between the true hedger and a speculator and the further studies are needed in order to clarify the issue.

Kamali’s view on speculation is that it is lawful, but “its propensity toward gambling must be tackled through constant supervision” (2007, p. 335; Kunhibava, 2008). Also,

⁵ This *hadith* is considered *sahih* according to Muslim’s condition.

according to the resolution by the Shari'ah Advisory Council (SAC) of Securities Commission (SC) the speculation is permissible under Islamic jurisprudence (SAC, 2007, p. 109). Being highly leveraged, Bacha (2003) says, financial derivatives are inclined towards speculation and “by not being able to hedge with these instruments and [thus] exposing one’s wealth to otherwise easily manageable risks, is being imprudent and equally irresponsible as speculation is.” Hence, the possibility of speculation in the derivatives market is, beyond doubt, a matter of fact. However, there is also a possibility to design the necessary tools and means to prevent such practices (El Gari, 1993).

To somehow prevent the speculation and gambling, Al-Saati (2002) proposed the use of minimum price fluctuation or “tick size” as well as to introduce daily price limit that will curb the price movement for a given day. Furthermore, the standardization of the contract will further restrict the possibilities of speculation, gambling and uncertainty (*gharar*) while at the same time it will promote liquidity in the market (Al-Saati, 2002). Therefore, according to Dusuki “a more detailed guidelines or parameters (*dhawābit*) are necessary to make sure that this product [Islamic swap or any other derivative instrument] is used solely for the purpose of hedging and not for speculative activities” (Dusuki, 2009).

6. Conclusion

From the discussion above, it is clear that true hedging aims at neutralising or minimising the risks involved in financial activities. As such, it falls under the umbrella of the objectives of *Shari'ah* and is desirable. However, Islamic finance should learn the lessons from the current global crisis and establish a system of rules and regulations that will serve the *maslaha* (public good) in general. This system should be subject to regulation and overview by a special body, with authority to interfere when necessary. Underlying assets should be attached to the trading activities, and these trades should be limited to the original buyers and sellers to avoid the speculative appetite of market gamblers. The sellers of hedge instruments should be specialised institutions that are subject to the required reserves too. Furthermore, the activities of derivatives market players should be transparent, and the data should be available for tracking. Although these steps may hamper the derivatives market and reduce its volume, they will protect players

from future volatilities, as well as provide a more stable and more sustainable system that is less vulnerable to the greed and thirst of market speculators and gamblers.

The main objections to the permissibility of the Islamic derivative instruments – according to those who oppose them – are the existence of the *gharar* and speculative nature of the instruments. Although the hedging *per se* is allowed in Islam, the use of derivatives for speculative gains is not (Mohamad, 2009). When it comes to *gharar*, as we mentioned earlier, there are some transactions that involve light *gharar* but are permissible due to the *maslahah*. On the other hand, it is believed that any investment carries an element of speculation and according to Mohd Daud Bakar the speculation is a matter of degree and as such cannot be prohibited entirely (Mohamad, 2009, p. 8).

In short, although the financial derivatives may involve the *gharar*, it is believed that by properly structuring these instruments, using *istihsān* and *maslahah*, we can stipulate necessary conditions as to reduce the *gharar* to an acceptable level (Al-Saati, 2003).

Finally, paper gives an overview of the current debate on Islamic derivatives and discusses the major contention points. In order to make this research even stronger a deeper analysis of the speculation and *fiqhi* issues is needed.

Wallahu a'lamu!

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